

Utaina

Connecting Aotearoa Through Digitised Sounds and Stories

Utaina

A collaborative project of Archives New Zealand (ArchivesNZ), the National Library of New Zealand (NLNZ) and Ngā Taonga Sound & Vision (NTSV) to digitally preserve more than 400,000 items of Aotearoa New Zealand's Crown-owned at-risk audiovisual magnetic media.

Balancing Complexities and Scale

Scale

ArchivesNZ and NLNZ - Digitised over **70,000** items (73,000 playback hours) across 13 formats within 5 years.

Preservation Format & Digital Storage

FFV1/MKV lossless compression as preservation video format to counter digital storage cost pressure. Storage size savings up to **50%**.

Collection Discovery & Description

Fresh collections & holdings rediscovery uncovered over **20,000** previously undescribed and inaccessible items.

Logistics

Movement and tracking of over **1,000** items weekly at every stage from packing to digitisation and back on shelves.

Quality Control

Strategic and scalable QC—automated validation and statistical sampling—enabled us to meet preservation standards within strict workflow deadlines.

Impact

Digitised audiovisual items now accessible virtually and internationally.

Some items previously found with mould now cleaned and digitised.

Ruru Karaitiana (left), the composer of 'Blue Smoke', and Garry Mutton B Mus, photographed ca 1969 by Brian Bell, (PAColl-4090-3) Alexander Turnbull Library
Blue Smoke 12" lacquer disc with the inscription 'I am greatly honoured Ruru Karaitiana.' (Archives ID: R26274107 AAPG 22244). Archives New Zealand

Culturally significant audiovisual items are rediscovered and made accessible.

Reconnecting researchers to collections made by their family, or on labels that are defunct and previously not available anywhere.

Preserving the nation's memory and record of our Government - snapshots of how the state once imagined its relationship with people and the land.